

A comparative study of dark matter flow & hydrodynamic turbulence and its applications

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Preface

Dark matter, if exists, accounts for five times as much as ordinary baryonic matter. Therefore, dark matter flow might possess the widest presence in our universe. The other form of flow, hydrodynamic turbulence in air and water, is without doubt the most familiar flow in our daily life. During the pandemic, we have found time to think about and put together a systematic comparison for the connections and differences between two types of flow, both of which are typical non-equilibrium systems.

The goal of this presentation is to leverage this comparison for a better understanding of the nature of dark matter and its flow behavior on all scales. Science should be open. All comments are welcome.

Thank you!

Data repository and relevant publications

Structural (halo-based) approach:

0.	Data https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6541230
1.	Inverse mass cascade in dark matter flow and effects on halo mass functions https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.09985
2.	Inverse mass cascade in dark matter flow and effects on halo deformation, energy, size, and density profiles https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.12244
3.	Inverse energy cascade in self-gravitating collisionless dark matter flow and effects of halo shape https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.13885
4.	The mean flow, velocity dispersion, energy transfer and evolution of rotating and growing dark matter halos https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2201.12665
5.	Two-body collapse model for gravitational collapse of dark matter and generalized stable clustering hypothesis for pairwise velocity https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.05784
6.	Evolution of energy, momentum, and spin parameter in dark matter flow and integral constants of motion https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.04054
7.	The maximum entropy distributions of velocity, speed, and energy from statistical mechanics of dark matter flow https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.03126
8.	Halo mass functions from maximum entropy distributions in collisionless dark matter flow https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2110.09676

Statistics (correlation-based) approach:

0.	Data https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569898
1.	The statistical theory of dark matter flow for velocity, density, and potential fields https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.00910
2.	The statistical theory of dark matter flow and high order kinematic and dynamic relations for velocity and density correlations https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.02991
3.	The scale and redshift variation of density and velocity distributions in dark matter flow and two-thirds law for pairwise velocity https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.06515
4.	Dark matter particle mass and properties from two-thirds law and energy cascade in dark matter flow https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2202.07240
5.	The origin of MOND acceleration and deep-MOND from acceleration fluctuation and energy cascade in dark matter flow https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.05606
6.	The baryonic-to-halo mass relation from mass and energy cascade in dark matter flow https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.06899

Structural (halo-based) approach for dark matter flow

Inverse mass cascade in dark matter flow and effects on halo mass functions

Xu Z., 2021, arXiv:2109.12244v1 [astro-ph.CO]
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.12244>

Introduction

Review: In hydrodynamic turbulence, “[energy cascade](#)” involves the energy transfer from large eddies to small eddies with a scale-independent rate of energy cascade.

The dark matter flow, a self-gravitating collisionless flow, involves **a continuous mass transfer from small to large mass scales** with a scale-independent rate of mass cascade ϵ_m .

- Goal 1: [Identify and formulate mass cascade](#)
- Goal 2: [Explore the random walk of halos in mass space](#)
- Goal 3: [Derive the halo mass function based on the theory of mass cascade](#)

- Identify all halos of different sizes
- Group halos according to the halo size n_p
- [Mass flow across halo groups from small to large mass scale \(inverse\)](#) through the merging with “single merger”
- [Cascade leads to random-walk of halos in mass space](#)

Mass redistribution among halo groups

Backward function: fraction of mass inherited from all other halo groups at an earlier time

Forward function: fraction of mass passed to all other halo groups at a later time

Minus sign

 Backward mass redistribution function
 Forward mass redistribution function

= Net mass redistribution function

Properties/features of mass cascade

Forward mass redistribution function

Backward mass redistribution function

- *Local: cascade is local in mass space*
Halos inherit/pass their mass mostly from/to halos of the same or similar size.
(energy cascade in turbulence is also local in wavenumber space)

Properties of mass cascade

Net mass redistribution function

Net mass redistribution function D_{NM} :
 <0 : inherit more mass than pass mass
 >0 : pass more mass than inherit mass
 Sum of $D_{NM} = 0$

Net effect: halos transfers mass from below to above.

- *Asymmetric: cascade is two-way in mass space but not symmetric*
- *Inverse: from small to large mass scales*

(energy cascade in turbulence is a direct cascade from large to small scales)

Time and mass scales in inverse mass cascade

Average waiting time of a merging event with a single merger in a given halo group of halo mass m_h

$$\tau_h(m_h, a)$$

The rate at which mass is passed up from this group:

$$\varepsilon_m \sim -m_h / \tau_h$$

Average waiting time (halo lifespan) of a merging event for a given halo in halo group with n_h halos of mass m_h

$$\tau_g(m_h, a) = n_h \tau_h = -\frac{m_h n_h}{\varepsilon_m} = -\frac{m_g}{\varepsilon_m}$$

Average time required to form halo of mass m_h via a sequence of merging events (n_p times):

$$\tau_f(m_h, a) = \tau_g n_p = \tau_g m_h / m_p$$

Time required to cascade entire mass M_h in all halos:

$$\tau_M(a) = -M_h(a) / \varepsilon_m(a) \sim t$$

Time required to form halo of a characteristic mass m_h^* should be on the order of the current physical time t :

$$\tau_f(m_h^*, a) \sim t$$

$$\tau_M(a) \geq \tau_f(m_h, a) \geq \tau_g(m_h, a) \geq \tau_h(m_h, a)$$

$$m_h^* \sim \frac{M_h(a) m_p}{n_h^* m_h^*} \sim -\frac{\varepsilon_m(a)}{H n_h^* n_p^*}$$

Chain reaction description of mass cascade

“Little halos have big halos, That feed on their mass; And big halos have greater halos, And so on to growth”

Chain reactions provide non-equilibrium systems a potential mechanism to continuously release energy and increase the system entropy.

- Mass cascade is Local, Asymmetric, Inverse;
- Justifies a chain reaction description of mass cascade;
- The initial stage: initiation/generation of the chain carriers (free radicals)
- The propagation stage: a sequence of accretion of single mergers to propagate the mass along the reaction chain
- The termination stage: the deposition of the mass cascaded from the scales below to grow halos

Formulating mass cascade

Mass flux function (kg/s):
total mass flux from all
halos below m_h

Mass flux function: $\Pi_m(m_h, a)$

Total mass of all halos: $M_h(a)$

Halo mass function: $f_M(m_h, a)$

Halo group mass: $m_g(m_h, a)$

$$\Pi_m(m_h, a) = -\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left[M_h(a) \int_{m_h}^{\infty} f_M(m, m_h^*) dm \right]$$

Mass transfer function (1/s): rate of mass transfer for halos of mass m_h

$$T_m(m_h, a) = \frac{\partial \Pi_m(m_h, a)}{\partial m_h} = \frac{\partial \left[M_h(a) f_M(m_h, m_h^*) \right]}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial m_g(m_h, a)}{m_p \partial t}$$

Halo mass: m_h

Particle mass: m_p

In mass propagation range: $m_h \ll m_h^*$

$$\mathcal{E}_m(a) = \Pi_m(m_h, a) \quad \leftarrow$$

$$T_m(m_h, a) = \frac{\partial m_g(m_h, a)}{m_p \partial t} = 0 \quad m_g(m_h) \equiv m_g(m_h, a) \quad \leftarrow$$

- Rate of mass cascade is Mass-scale independent;
- Halo group mass is time-independent (steady-state);

Halo group mass and mass flux function

Halo group mass $m_g(m_h, a)$
(time-independent in mass propagation range)

Mass flux function $\Pi_m(m_h, a)$ (normalized by Nm_p/t_0) varying with halo size
(scale-independent in mass propagation range)

Formulating mass cascade

In mass propagation range: $m_h \ll m_h^*$

$$\varepsilon_m(a) = \Pi_m(m_h = 0, a) = -\frac{\partial M_h(a)}{\partial t}$$

$$\varepsilon_m(a) = -m_h f_h(m_h, a)$$

$$f_h(m_h, a) = \underbrace{f_0(a) M_h(a) f_M(m_h, m_h^*(a))}_{1} \underbrace{\frac{m_p}{m_h} \left(\frac{m_h}{m_p} \right)^\lambda}_{2}$$

Term 1: proportional to the number of halos in group;

Term 2: proportional surface area of halo in group;

$$\lambda \approx 2/3$$

Merging frequency for halo group:

$$f_h(m_h, a)$$

Halo geometry parameter:

$$\lambda$$

Fundamental frequency for merging of two single mergers:

$$f_0(a) \propto a^{-\tau_0}$$

Independent variables: m_h a

Free parameters: m_p λ τ_0

Formulating mass cascade

In mass propagation range: $m_h \ll m_h^*$

Dimensional analysis requires mass function: $f_M(m_h, m_h^*) = \beta_0 m_h^{-\lambda} (m_h^*)^{\lambda-1}$

Table 2. List of dependence on the scale factor a for different values of τ_0 and λ

λ	τ_0	f_0	ε_m	M_h	f_M	m_h^*	τ_h^*	n_h^*	m_g^*	τ_g^*
λ	τ_0	$a^{-\tau_0}$	$a^{-\tau_0}$	$a^{3/2-\tau_0}$	$a^{\tau_0-3/2}$	$\frac{(3/2-\tau_0)}{a^{(1-\lambda)}}$	$\frac{(3/2-\lambda\tau_0)}{a^{(1-\lambda)}}$	$a^{-\left(\frac{3}{2}-\tau_0\right)\frac{(1+\lambda)}{(1-\lambda)}}$	$a^{-\left(\frac{3}{2}-\tau_0\right)\frac{\lambda}{(1-\lambda)}}$	$a^{\frac{(\tau_0-3\lambda/2)}{(1-\lambda)}}$
2/3	1	a^{-1}	a^{-1}	$a^{1/2}$	$a^{-1/2}$	$a^{3/2}$	$a^{5/2}$	$a^{-5/2}$	a^{-1}	a^0
2/3	1/2	$a^{-1/2}$	$a^{-1/2}$	a^1	a^{-1}	a^3	$a^{7/2}$	a^{-5}	a^{-2}	$a^{-3/2}$
3/4	1	a^{-1}	a^{-1}	$a^{1/2}$	$a^{-1/2}$	a^2	a^3	$a^{-7/2}$	$a^{-3/2}$	$a^{-1/2}$

The halo mass for type II halos (the dominant type for large halos, Fig. 2 in ref. [1]) exhibits a power law scaling

Dependence on halo mass m_h and mass resolution m_p

Table 3. List of dependence on the halo mass m_h

f_M	ε_m	f_h	τ_h	τ_g	τ_f	m_g	n_h
$m_h^{-\lambda}$	m_h^0	m_h^{-1}	m_h^1	$m_h^{-\lambda}$	$m_h^{1-\lambda}$	$m_h^{-\lambda}$	$m_h^{-1-\lambda}$

Fundamental frequency f_0 for merging between two single mergers depends on particle mass (same as cosmological redshift for photon frequency $f \sim a^{-1}$):

Table 4. List of dependence on the mass resolution m_p

f_M	f_h	τ_f	ε_m	τ_h^*	τ_h	m_h^*	M_h	c_0	β_0
m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0	m_p^0
n_h	τ_g	m_g	n_p	f_0	b_0	λ_0	n_h^*	m_g^*	n_p^*
m_p	m_p	m_p	m_p^{-1}	$m_p^{\lambda-1}$	$m_p^{\lambda-1}$	$m_p^{1-\lambda}$	m_p	m_p	m_p^{-1}

$$f_0 \propto a^{-1} m_p^{-1/3}$$

Can we detect f_0 from any experiment or observation?

Random walk of halos and halo mass function

Merging frequency
for halo group:

$$f_h(m_h, a)$$

Characteristic
merging time for
halo group:

$$\tau_h(m_h, a) = 1/f_h$$

Characteristic
merging time
(lifetime) for a
given halo:
waiting time to
merge

of halos in group

$$\tau_g(m_h, a) = n_h \tau_h$$

The exponential
distribution of
waiting time to
merge:

$$P(\tau_{gr}) = \frac{1}{\tau_g} \exp\left(-\frac{\tau_{gr}}{\tau_g}\right)$$

1D Random walk equation in mass space:

$$\frac{\partial m_h(t)}{\partial t} = \frac{m_p \xi(t)}{\tau_g(m_h)} = \sqrt{2D_p(m_h)} \zeta(t)$$

Fokker-Planck equation for distribution function:

$$\frac{\partial P_h}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial m_h} \left[\sqrt{D_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial m_h} (\sqrt{D_p} P_h) \right] = D_{p0} \frac{\partial}{\partial m_h} \left[m_h^\lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial m_h} (m_h^\lambda P_h) \right]$$

Halo mass function:

$$f_M(m_h, a) = \frac{(1-\lambda)}{\sqrt{\pi\eta_0}} \left(\frac{m_h^*}{m_h}\right)^\lambda \frac{1}{m_h^*} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{4\eta_0} \left(\frac{m_h}{m_h^*}\right)^{2-2\lambda}\right]$$

Reduce to Press-Schechter (PS) mass function if $\lambda=2/3$!

Double- λ mass function from mass cascade

λ : halo geometry parameter; naturally, we can have different λ for different range.

λ_1 for mass propagation range (small halos);

λ_2 for mass deposition range (large halos);

$$f_M(m_h, a) = \frac{(1-\lambda)}{\sqrt{\pi\eta_0}} \left(\frac{m_h^*}{m_h}\right)^{\lambda_1} \frac{1}{m_h^*} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{4\eta_0} \left(\frac{m_h}{m_h^*}\right)^{2+2\lambda_2}\right]$$

Double- λ mass function:

$$f_{D\lambda}(\nu) = \frac{(2\sqrt{\eta_0})^{-q}}{\Gamma(q/2)} \nu^{q/2-1} \exp\left(-\frac{\nu}{4\eta_0}\right)$$

- PS mass function
- ST model (modified PS) from ellipsoid collapse
- JK mass function by data fitting
- More generally, λ_1 can be a function of halo mass m_h

Comparison between different mass functions and simulation

Summary and key words

Hydrodynamic turbulence	Dark matter flow	Mass redistribution
Direct energy cascade from large to small length scales	Inverse mass cascade from small to large mass scales	Random walk
“inertial range” & “dissipation range”	propagation range & deposition range	Heterogeneous diffusion
		Waiting time
		Chain-reaction
		Halo mass function

- Strong connections between dark matter flow and hydrodynamic turbulence
- The mass cascade is local, two-way, and asymmetric in mass space
- Scale-independent rate of mass cascade and time-independent halo group mass
- Chain reaction description for mass cascade to release energy and maximize entropy
- Random-walk of halos in mass space with an exponential distribution of waiting time
- Press-Schechter mass function is a special solution from halo random-walk
- New Double- λ halo mass function (based on the mass cascade)
- Extend double- λ halo mass function to consider λ as some function of halo size.